

Currents in Biochemistry

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It is a very striking fact that biochemistry makes wonderful progress in fields in which it has already been very successful, while it makes no progress at all in fields which seem entirely obscure today. If we study these two groups of problems, we will find that the problems in which biochemistry had been, and still is, successful, can all be expressed with symbols of classical chemistry, letters and dashes, while the problems in which we make no progress cannot be expressed in these terms. The reactions belonging to the first group can be repeated in homogeneous solutions, while those of the second involve complicated systems in what looks to be a solid state, linked to structure. To be more specific, biochemistry was most successful in the analysis of intermediary metabolism, in the isolation and the constitution analysis of hormones, vitamins or antibiotics, but remained entirely unsuccessful in the understanding of phenomena like muscle contraction which involves the changes in the physical state of a contractile system. It remained unsuccessful in the analysis of nervous activity which involves electric work in the membranes. The same holds for the establishment of secretions which all involve osmotic work, gradients against concentration. All these latter phenomena not only involve structure but also involve transformation and energy which suggests that our knowledge is deficient in the understanding of the nature of energy.

Physics has given up, a long time ago, asking what things are, and limits itself to asking how things behave. The human mind being built to distinguish things of our own dimension, is entirely unfit to understand the real nature of things, the units of which are very far below the limits of our perception. For this reason physics, limiting itself to the analysis of behaviour, is content with expressing itself in terms of mathematics. The biochemist cannot be satisfied with mathematical formulas because he is dealing with living matter, with particles of one size or another, and his thinking has to be linked to structures, that is, to orientation in space. So, we are led into the problem of the relation of structure and energy. The failure of biochemistry to understand the complex phenomena indicates that our outlook on this relation is wrong. Why it should be so is easy to see. Biochemistry went into bloom at the end of the last century when the atom was an indivisible unit, and the molecule structure built of these atoms. So the biochemical thinking became dominated by the molecular concept which can be represented by the different structural formulas composed of letters and dashes, by which the organic chemists mostly express themselves. However, one feels instinctively that the structure, which forms the foundation of the living machinery, involves the "solid state" and in solid state physics the molecules disappear, more or less, as units. So, already 20 years ago I made an attempt to apply the ideas of solid states to the living structure hoping to arrive at a better understanding. This attempt, however, remained unsuccessful and did not lead to a better understanding and I can see, today, why. The "solid state" dealt with by the physicists, involves the idea of the very regular repetition of identical units. If these

units are close to one another, the potential barriers may break down and the whole system may fuse into one single unit. The most classical example of such a unit may be copper wire which may be miles long, which conducts electricity, which means that an electron put on one molecule of this unit at one end can be tapped off at the other end within a very short period, indicating that the whole system is, in a way, not an agglomeration of molecules but one single unit, into which these molecules have fused. The reason why this idea was not applicable to biochemistry is easy to see. In biochemistry we do not have the high geometric regularity which we find in crystals, and second, which is equally important, the units are not identical, repetitive. For instance, in the oxidative chain the electrons are known to go from nucleotides to riboflavine, from riboflavine to a cytochrome, from here to another, a third or fourth, and eventually to oxygen. There are also other similar chains which comprise succinic acid, quinones, etc. In any case, the units forming the whole chains are not identical. So, the solid state idea is not applicable to biochemistry and some other means have to be found to understand the intimate relations within a living solid structure in which electrons have a certain mobility, which means that the barriers between the single molecules, and with this the whole molecular concept, break down to some extent. Needless to say, the living material is built of molecules because once we pull the structure into bits we arrive at molecules. But this does not mean that the molecules do not form some sort of supermolecular units, and the rigid molecular concept can be applied to living matter.

Searching for a physical basis for a better approach, I was especially fascinated, during the last years, by "charge transfer". The idea of charge transfer should not be confused with the idea of a transfer of an electron. Any oxidoreduction involves transfer of electrons; but this is not charge transfer. The idea of charge transfer was expressed first by Joseph Weiss in 1942 who found that in certain complexes the one partner of a molecular complex may use the orbitals of the other partner and the donor molecule within this complex may transfer an electron from its ground state to the first empty excited level of the acceptor. This idea was given later a quantum mechanical foundation by the extensive work of Mulliken. The electron may be partly transferred, or be completely transferred, it may need extraneous energy for the transfer, or may go over spontaneously and once it goes over various things may happen to it. The simplest thing which can happen is that the two molecules, the acceptor and the donor, part, interacting with the solvent. The result of this parting will be the production of two free radicals, and free radicals are known to be very reactive. But this is, by no means, the only possibility. The electron transferred on to the acceptor may be transferred from this acceptor to another acceptor. The first acceptor now acts as a donor. From the second acceptor the electron may go to the third, etc. So the electron may go from molecule to molecule once there are certain conditions fulfilled, of which the most important is a very close proximity, which makes the overlap of orbitals possible. Possibly the oxidative chain in biology is, essentially, such a wandering of single electrons from one molecule to another. Since the orbitals overlap, the idea of molecular identity, within this system, becomes very fuzzy and what we actually have in hand is one single electronic system, in which electrons have a more or less free mobility. This leads to a new biochemistry without chemistry, if we understand, by chemistry, changes in which the orbitals and electronic distributions are rearranged. Such a wandering of electrons does not involve covalent changes. The molecules simply form a quantum mechanical framework, on which electrons can move. It seems very likely to me that the living structures are actually such a quantum mechanical framework in which the molecular identity becomes of secondary importance.

I feel very strongly that one is not lost here, entirely, in abstruse speculation. I am

supported in this conviction by a little observation I have made lately. I have found that the carcinogenic substances, that is, the substances which produce cancer, distinguish themselves from other non-carcinogenic substances by the ease by which they give off one electron. This specific quality is evident even in cases in which we compare carcinogenic substances with very closely related homologues which are not carcinogenic and which will be found not to give off electrons under similar conditions. These experiments will be reported in one of the next issues of the Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences in Washington. In any case, this little experience convinces me that we are not lost here in abstruse speculation but have to do with phenomena which are very closely related, not only to biological processes, but also to everyday problems of medicine.

I actually think that at present there is a new biochemistry being born, built on ideas of wave mechanics. I have, myself, put down my experience in two little books, the one called "Bioenergetics" and the other "Submolecular Biology" in '57 and '60 (Academic Press, New York). Though these little books may be one of the swallows indicating the approach of the new spring, I am, in no way, alone in this new field. An increasing number of research people are engaged in this field. I would mention, in the first place, the Pullmans in Paris who were the first to establish a relation between electronic distribution and carcinogenicity. I would mention B. Commoner of St. Louis who found close relations between photosynthesis, enzymatic activity and related phenomena and electron spin resonance. So, I do think that a new biochemistry is in the process of being born, a biochemistry which relies less on the ideas of classical chemistry than on the ideas of quantum mechanics. I expect that a great forward leap in biochemistry will come when this new line of research will be more generally adopted.

It is a great privilege to offer these few lines to the memory of the Founder-President of the Indian Chemical Society, late Professor P. C. Ray.